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BEHAVIORAL AND DEVELOPMENTAL CHARACTERISTICS OF A CHILD WITH MILD AUTISM SPECTRUM DISORDER - A CASE STUDY

Authors

**Yvonne M. Porazo, Geizelle R. Villamor, Scott T. Bantaculo,
Mariya Czarina L. Artugue, Annabelle A. Dela Rama**

Lanaguage and Literature Unit
Abuyog Community College

Abstract

This qualitative single case study examines the behavioral and developmental characteristics of a young male child diagnosed with mild autism spectrum disorder (ASD), currently enrolled in a Special Education (SPED) program in a rural community in Abuyog, Leyte, Philippines. The child was born prematurely at 32 weeks of gestation following maternal stress, required post-natal incubation, and subsequently exhibited notable delays in motor and language development. Formal recognition of his condition occurred only upon school entry when behavioral differences were observed by his classroom teacher. Data were collected through a semi-structured interview with the child's mother and multiple sessions of structured behavioral observation using a researcher-constructed checklist. The results indicate a mixed profile: the child has a lot of problems, for example, hyperactivity, short attention span, unclear speech, unsupervised wandering, decreased pain sensitivity, and disturbed daily routines, even though at the same time he shows relative strengths, such as social involvement, particularly with older peers. Current literature examining the literature about mild ASD presentation and the criteria for established ASD diagnosis are reviewed in relation to these behaviors. The study concludes with evidence-based recommendations to involve the family, control behavior, assist in communication, and intervene in education. Limitations of the study and directions for future research are also discussed.

Keywords: *Autism Spectrum Disorder, developmental delay, behavioral characteristics, qualitative case study, special education, sensory processing*

INTRODUCTION

Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) is a complex neurodevelopmental condition characterized by persistent difficulties in social communication and interaction, as well as restricted, repetitive patterns of behavior, interests, and activities (American Psychiatric Association [APA], 2013). It can be severe or mild with high functioning profiles, and while it may not be noticeable in terms of cognitive or communication problems, it can still mean that the person has trouble functioning in social, school, and other settings (Lord et al., 2018). While ASD is increasingly recognized across the globe and is estimated to affect 1 in 36 children in the U.S. (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention [CDC], 2023), on-time detection and timely intervention remain significant challenges, particularly in low-resource environments.

The implementation of early intervention programs, professional educators and diagnostic services does not yet equally address the needs of all children in the Philippines, particularly those in the rural areas (Department of Education, 2019). According to Zwaigenbaum et al. (2015), many children with autism spectrum disorder (ASD) are first

officially diagnosed until they start school, which may cause them to miss crucial times for early intervention. This highlights the importance of community-based research that is situated within the context of the community to deepen the understanding and address the developmental needs of children with ASD in underprivileged communities.

In addition to the diagnostic delay issue, the most common and abundant literature published on ASD has been population-based, quantitative or trend-detecting literature, which is beneficial to understanding prevalence and identifying general patterns but less effective in understanding the complex and individual ways that ASD may manifest in specific developmental and socio-environmental contexts (Yin, 2014).

The known relationship between prenatal risk factors and outcomes for ASD provides another reason to explore our study. The number of studies linking ASD and increased risk for neurodevelopmental disorders with a high incidence of pre-term birth and neonatal difficulties is increasing (Johnson & Marlow, 2011; Gardener et al., 2011). It would be useful to understand the developmental trajectory of a child who has been exposed to several of these risk factors and to determine the types of support that can be used to help prevent the appearance of ASD-related traits and the types of factors that may be responsible for such traits.

The current study aims to contribute to the lack of context-specific and qualitative documentation of ASD in rural contexts in the Philippines by conducting a thorough behavioral and developmental case study of a child diagnosed with mild ASD in Barangay Buntay, Abuyog, Leyte. The purpose of this study is to develop an extensive individual profile that can be used for meaningful, locally relevant recommendations for action, based on the child's developmental history, behavioural traits, sensory reactions and everyday functioning, which is gained via both the parent interview and direct observation.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

This study seeks to answer the following research questions:

1. What is the child's prenatal, perinatal, and early developmental history, and how may these factors relate to the emergence of ASD-related characteristics?
2. What behavioral patterns are consistently observed in the child across home and community settings?
3. What specific challenges does the child encounter in daily life, including in communication, social interaction, attention, sensory processing, and routine management?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The qualitative single-case study method was particularly appropriate for the present study because it was used to answer the questions of "how" and "why" in a real-world phenomenon or complex event in its natural context. The design selected is a case study as it enables a holistic and contextualized assessment of the child's behavioural and developmental profile, provides a range of evidence to arrive at a comprehensive picture, and is not achievable with an experimental or quantitative approach. The method aligns with interpretive paradigm where statistical generalization has less weight than a deep and descriptive understanding of an individual's experiences (Creswell, 2013).

Methodological triangulation was used to enhance the credibility of this study by comparing information obtained through the parental interview and information obtained through the direct behavioral observation.

Research Participant

The participant is a young male youngster with mild ASD who is presently enrolled in a Special Education (SPED) program after being referred by a teacher. To preserve his anonymity, he is known as "Renz". Renz was born around 32 weeks prematurely because of the stress of her mother during pregnancy. He required postnatal incubation and in his early life he was clearly impaired in both his expressive language (speaking) and gross motor skills (walking). His problem was only detected when he began school. His instructor saw actions that weren't typical of his age-matched friends and suggested that he be placed in a special education program.

The study subject was selected on the basis of criterion sampling due to his meeting the specific criterion of being a child diagnosed with autism spectrum disorder (ASD) by a credentialed developmental pediatrician. However, he was chosen because the purpose of the study, to understand how the child with mild ASD behaved and developed in a natural environment, is directly related to his situation (Palinkas et al., 2015).

Research Instruments

For collecting the data, two complimentary tools were used. To gain a deeper understanding of Renz's prenatal and perinatal history, milestones of development, behaviors in the home setting, routines, sensory responses, and family experiences of the child's diagnosis and SPED placement, a semi-structured interview guide was first developed by the researcher. To enable the mother to expound on her observations and experiences without being limited by predefined response categories, open-ended questions were given priority (Kvale, 2007). To encourage organic and thorough responses, the interview was done in the local tongue (Cebuano/Waray).

Second, a structured behavioral observation checklist was developed to guide systematic documentation of the child's behavior across naturalistic settings. Key behavioral domains, such as (a) social interaction and communication behaviors, (b) attention and hyperactivity, (c) sensory processing responses, (d) repetitive or restricted behaviors, and (e) safety-related behaviors (e.g., wandering), were used to organize the checklist based on DSM-5 ASD criteria and pertinent literature. As both tools were designed to complement each other, it was possible to cross reference data from the two sources.

Validation of Research Instruments

The material of both instruments was validated before data collection. They were validated by two qualified validators: one faculty member who has experience in the technique of qualitative research, and one special education professional. All of the instruments were profiled by validators on the following criteria: being linguistically clear, adequate for content, culturally appropriate for the intended audience, and consistent with accepted behavioral frameworks of ASD. To reflect current and evidence-based views of presentation of ASD, unnecessary items were removed, and item wording was revised following the validation process.

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Locale of the Study

The study was conducted in Barangay Buntay, Abuyog, Leyte, Philippines which is in the participant's neighborhood. The location is rural and was selected for its contextual value, and because it is representative of a community that has a low level of access to specialist programs for education and development. Ecological validity of the behavioral observations was supported by the study being done in the child's home and immediate community. This enabled the child's behaviors to be documented in real and natural environments, rather than in artificial or clinical situations.

Ethical Considerations

In this work, the principle of the standard ethical rules used in research involving human subject were adhered to and special care was taken to ensure the safety of a child with a developmental disability. The child's mother received a detailed verbal and written explanation of the purpose, methodology and use of the data from this study before data collection. She was also told that she can revoke her consent at any time, with no consequences. Informed consent in writing was obtained. They were unable to obtain formal consent from the child, as was the case with a participant, because of this child's developmental stage and age; however, during the observation sessions the researchers monitored for potential signs of discomfort or distress and would have discontinued the observation if these signs had been observed.

To protect the participant's identity and privacy, and that of his family, all written correspondence is anonymized and does not reveal any personally identifiable information. All information collected (e.g., transcripts, observation notes, notes of interviews) was stored safely, shared only with the research team and used solely for this investigation.

Data Gathering Procedure

Data collection was divided into several stages. First, the researchers were in touch with the family due to a school recommendation for the subject to inform them about the study and request their participation. Once informed consent was obtained a schedule was set up for interview and observation sessions at times and places that were suitable to the family.

The mother was interviewed for approximately 60 to 90 minutes, in a semi-structured format. The session was audio-taped with her permission to ensure that the tape would be transcribed correctly. Each of the five systematic behavioral observation sessions was conducted for 45-60 minutes during 3 weeks after the interview in different settings such as the child's home and the nearby neighborhood. The behavioral checklist was used to document the behaviors and observers made detailed field notes, documenting specific behaviors, context, frequency, and duration. Variability in behavior related to daily routine was captured by scheduling observation sessions at different times of the day.

Data Analysis

The data was analyzed using thematic analysis, a six-phase model introduced by Braun and Clarke (2006): (1) familiarization with the data through repeated reading of interview transcripts and observation notes; (2) generation of initial codes labeling significant behavioral and developmental features; (3) searching for themes by clustering related codes; (4)

reviewing and refining themes against the full dataset; (5) defining and naming themes; and (6) producing the written analysis. The themes were then analyzed using the criteria for the diagnosis of ASD from the DSM-5 and relevant empirical research to contextualize the results in the broader context of the literature.

The triangulation process was done by systematically analyzing the patterns throughout the behavioral observation sessions with themes found in the interview data. When results agreed there was greater confidence in addressing the results; when results were different, they were noted and may have been due to a different context within the home and community setting or due to uncertainty in the child's behavioral state from one event to the next.

Results and Discussion

Following careful data analysis and close observation of the issue, the following themes become apparent.

Perinatal Risk Factors and Early Developmental Delays

Renz was born at around 32 weeks gestation during a pregnancy that was exacerbated by a lot of stress for the mother. As a newborn, he had to be kept in the incubator. His mother observed that as he grew, he was delayed in both his expressive language (speaking) and gross motor skills (walking) that became more apparent when compared to other children of the same age.

These results are in line with the body of research that shows a connection between increased neurodevelopmental risk and preterm birth as well as stress during pregnancy. Johnson and Marlow (2011) found that preterm infants are significantly more likely to suffer from a range of neuro-developmental issues, including problems with language development, attention problems, and behaviors associated with ASD. Gardener et al. (2011) have reported prenatal maternal stress as a standalone risk factor for ASD. In this case, co-occurrence of mother stress and preterm birth may have increased neurodevelopmental susceptibility. Because of the single case approach used in this study, it cannot be concluded that Renz's background is the direct cause of the problem, but it is remarkable and therapeutic that all of these are risk factors.

One common pattern found in moderate presentations of ASD is the late detection of the child's condition, as in the case of Renz, who was detected only during school admission (Zwaigenbaum et al., 2015). According to Dawson and Burner (2011), this delay has probably led to lost chances for early intervention during the most crucial stages of brain development.

Social Engagement — A Relative Strength

Renz is very proactive about engaging social contacts and is not afraid to do so, particularly with older children, based on observation and interview information. He was observed making eye contact and attempting to engage in play activities as well as responding positively to social interactions with familiar adults.

It is the social profile of children with mild or high functioning ASD that is different, and although social pragmatics and communication remain a challenge, social motivation may not be compromised or even enhanced (Happé & Frith, 2020). The older friends' preference may be a reflection of a desire for more controlled, predictable or prescriptive social

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interactions, as older children tend to be more proactive than younger ones in social encounters (which might reduce Renz's social-cognitive load). The results of these findings highlight the importance of individual assessment and contradict a simplistic description of ASD as a condition that is always characterized by social disengagement.

Communication Challenges

Renz's mother said he had difficulty speaking and that was confirmed by witnessing. He was unable to tell what he wanted and participate in turn taking conversations, because his oral communication is often unclear and difficult for unknown people to understand. Nonverbal communication techniques that were observed during the sessions with Renz were vocalizing, pointing and directing adults by the hand when verbal communication wasn't enough. Speech and language impairments are another common expressive and receptive symptom of ASD on the spectrum (Lord et al., 2018). Speech can be normal in individuals with mild ASD although it may include some atypical prosody or some articulation impairments or difficulty with language pragmatics. Renz's poor communication skills likely have him showing behaviors that he is frustrated with which can hinder his social and academic growth. He has not received formal speech and language intervention in his current intervention plan, which is a major drawback that needs to be rectified.

Theme 4: Hyperactivity, Inattention, and Behavioral Dysregulation

All observations showed high levels of motor activity, difficulty sustaining attention to a task, and frequent transitions between activities without apparent completion of activities, all of which were noted by parents. For example, he was observed watching videos on a mobile device, rapidly going from one video to another without paying attention to any for too long. This behavior trend can be an expression of attentional dysregulation, not preference.

Studies have shown that hyperactivity and inattention are associated with up to 50-70% of individuals with ASD who also meet the criteria for Attention-Deficit/Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) (Leitner, 2014). Because of the high rate of co-occurrence among these disorders, it is now possible to make both diagnoses simultaneously in the DSM-5. Renz's behavioral profile suggests that there should be more formal evaluation since the concomitant ADHD would have an important impact on intervention planning.

Safety Concerns — Unsupervised Wandering

Renz's tendency to move towards exits and community areas, often without regard for safety boundaries is like the mother's complaint that he often goes outside the house without letting anyone in the family know. This wandering or going away with someone else was much of a worry to the family.

It is known that wandering poses a safety risk to children with ASD; the Interactive Autism Network estimates that 49% of children with ASD wander at some point in their lives (Anderson, 2012). It increases the danger of serious injuries, including as drowning and auto accidents, and puts a lot of strain on caretakers.

Atypical Sensory Processing

One of the major findings of the interview and observation was Renz's responsiveness to pain, which had decreased. His mother says that when he injures himself with a fall, minor

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bump or bruise, which would cause most children to show a pain response, he does not. No reports of light, sound or other sensory stimulation hypersensitivity.

According to the DSM-5 (APA, 2013), sensory processing abnormalities, both hyper- and hyposensitivity to sensory input, is considered a basic feature of ASD. These abnormalities have been observed in all sensory modalities in children with ASD (Marco et al., 2011). Clinical concern is caused by hyposensitivity to pain because it could make it more difficult for the child to signal pain or illness using their usual behavior and make it more likely that the child will not be able to let others know if they are hurt. It is critical that persons providing care and education are fully informed of this finding to ensure that proper monitoring is carried out.

Renz was known to have an unusual and difficult weekday. After getting up quite early and active immediately, he often attempts to go out alone. He often tries to go out on his own after getting up very early and being active from the beginning. He often falls asleep in early evening (between 5 and 6 PM) that may indicate an irregular circadian rhythm. He is not the guy who's focused, he's the one who switches channels quickly and without stains on his fingers when it comes to using mobile technology.

Research estimates that 40%-80% of children with ASD have sleep problems (Mazurek & Sohl, 2016). Many of these individuals suffer from sleep disturbances. Addressing his sleep patterns could have a greater overall impact on Renz's functioning. Sleep disturbances are a bidirectional cause and effect relationship with behavioral problems, attention problems, and emotional problems during wakefulness.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

A young child in a rural village in the Philippines who has mild ASD has been thoroughly and contextually portrayed in this case study. According to the results, there is no one, universal description of ASD; rather, each case is unique and characterized by a wide range of symptoms. Renz has significant challenges with communication, attention, behavioral regulation, sensory processing and managing daily routines, but has strong abilities in social drive and engagement, which can serve as a foundation for intervention. His developmental history includes preterm birth, neonatal issues, and delayed diagnosis; this is consistent with the developmental history profile listed in the autism spectrum disorder literature and underscores the importance of having a community level awareness and early developmental screening.

Furthermore, the study highlights that there are significant challenges for families in rural areas in terms of access to the support systems available to their children with autism spectrum disorder (ASD). These challenges include restricted availability of specialist therapists, official diagnosis services, and parent training programs based on evidence. The creation of specific interventions for individual children is very important but filling these gaps at a system level is far more important.

Recommendations

Renz should receive a comprehensive speech-language evaluation and continue regular speech-language therapy to address articulation concerns and build functional communication; where a licensed speech therapist is not available, basic augmentative and alternative communication (AAC) techniques should be taught to SPED instructors and

parents. To reduce elopement risk, develop an individualized safety plan with the family and relevant community members, include visual boundary-awareness training, and make environmental modifications such as door alarms or secure fencing. Establish consistent home and school routines using visual supports and visual timetables to aid transitions and activity regulation. Provide sleep-hygiene education for the family emphasizing regular nighttime routines, reducing screen time before bed, and reasonable flexibility in morning routines. Arrange a formal evaluation for possible co-occurring ADHD, and meanwhile implement attention supports at home and school such as breaking tasks into smaller steps, scheduled movement breaks, and minimizing distractions. Because Renz shows hyposensitivity to pain, ensure all caregivers are informed and perform regular physical checks to detect unnoticed injuries. Finally, empower the mother and other family members with organized training in behavioral-management strategies and encourage parent-mediated therapies, which research supports as effective for children with ASD.

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